

Effectiveness of Implementing Blended Learning Method in Leadership Training at the Human Resource Development Agency of Gorontalo Province

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Nov 2024; Accepted: 10 Dec 2024; Published: 07 Jan 2025

Abstract: This study aims to determine and analyze the effectiveness of the implementation of the blended learning method in leadership training at the BPSDM of Gorontalo Province. The focus of the study includes indicators of goal achievement, integration, and adaptation based on Duncan's organizational effectiveness theory (1973). This study uses a qualitative research method with a descriptive approach. Data were collected through interviews, observations, and documentation, then analyzed with the stages of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The results of the study show: (1) Achievement of Goals: Although blended learning training provides flexibility in time and place, a busy schedule and lack of synchronization with the tasks and responsibilities of participants in their respective agencies hinder the achievement of training effectiveness. (2) Integration: The training socialization procedure which was only carried out at the beginning of the activity caused participants to have a poor understanding of the learning system, while the organizer's human resources were limited in mastering technology. (3) Adaptation: Implementers and facilitators face major challenges in adjusting the use of the Learning Management System (LMS) due to the lack of adequate training and supporting facilities and infrastructure. Although there are challenges in implementing the blended learning method, the results show great potential for this method in increasing training effectiveness if technological support, human resources, and socialization procedures are improved.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Blended learning, Leadership Training, ASN.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the competence of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is one of the strategic efforts in improving the quality of public services and encouraging government effectiveness. ASN as the main element in the bureaucracy is required to have competencies that are relevant to the needs of the organization, especially in the challenging era of globalization. Blended learning-based leadership training is one of the innovations implemented to answer these needs, combining online and offline learning methods to create a more flexible, effective, and efficient learning process.

The blended learning method has been introduced as a modern learning innovation for developing ASN competencies.[1]. Research by Yunhang and Hidayati (2023)[2]shows that this method has advantages in increasing the efficiency and accessibility of learning.

However, there are obstacles such as limited technological infrastructure, minimal knowledge of participants about learning technology, and low digital literacy of facilitators. This shows that the implementation of blended learning requires better support, both in terms of infrastructure and human resource readiness.

The implementation of the blended learning method at the BPSDM of Gorontalo Province is based on the Regulation of the State Administration Agency of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2023, which regulates the stages of training including independent learning, classical, and e-learning. This method allows participants to learn flexibly in the workplace or at the training location. However, data shows that the effectiveness of its implementation still needs to be improved. The pass rate of participants in the administrator leadership training (PKA) decreased from 100% in 2022 to 97.7% in 2023, indicating challenges in its implementation.

Table 1.2 Percentage of graduation of leadership training participants in 2021, 2022, and 2023

Training	Graduation rate		
	2021	2022	2023
Supervisory Leadership Training	95%	100%	100%
Administrator Leadership Training	97.5%	100%	97.7%

Source: Processed by researchers (2024)

According to Akhmadi (2021)[3], the effectiveness of blended learning depends on several factors, including the availability of adequate infrastructure, the facilitator's ability to manage learning, and a continuous evaluation system. Maninggar's (2020) research shows that although this method has great potential in leadership training, challenges such as communication in distance learning and lack of technological support remain significant barriers. In addition, the learning outcomes of this method are greatly influenced by the level of collaboration and interaction between participants and facilitators.

Erman (2020)[4]emphasizes the importance of effective competency development to improve organizational productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness. In this context, Duncan's (1973) theory of organizational effectiveness[5]becomes relevant to evaluate the implementation of blended learning-based training. Duncan proposed three main indicators: goal achievement, integration, and adaptation. Goal achievement reflects the extent to which training achieves the set goals. Integration shows the organization's ability to align procedures and communication between parties involved. Meanwhile, adaptation measures the extent to which the organization is able to adjust to changes in technology and the environment.

Based on these conditions, this study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the implementation of the blended learning method in leadership training at BPSDM Gorontalo Province. The focus of the study includes indicators of goal achievement, integration, and adaptation, with the hope of providing strategic recommendations to improve the quality of leadership training in the future.

2. THEORITICAL REVIEW

Public Administration

AdministrationPublic administration is the process of managing public resources and personnel organized to formulate, implement, and manage public policy.(Waldo, 1971) also believes that public administration is an organization and management of people in government to achieve predetermined goals.[6].According to Chandler and Plano (1988)[7], public administration is the art and science that aims to manage "public affairs" through coordination and improvement of organizational systems, human resources, and finances.

Public administration also includes various aspects of management that aim to provide public services efficiently and responsively.

1. Effectiveness Measure

According to Duncan in steers[8]stated that the measure of effectiveness in measuring program effectiveness, whether implemented by private or government agencies, consists of 3 aspects, including:namely: 1) Achievement of Goals:namely achievement is the whole effort to achieve the goal must be viewed as a process. Therefore, in order to ensure the achievement of the final goal, stages are needed, both in the sense of stages of achieving its parts and stages in the sense of its periodization. Achievement of goals consists of indicators, namely the period of achievement is determined, achievement of targets as concrete targetsMeasuring the extent to which organizational goals are achieved, including the success of implementing training within a specified time frame, achieving targets, and compliance with implementation guidelines. 2) Integration:namely the measurement of the level of ability of an organization to carry out activities from the agreed work program and conduct socialization with other parties. Integration consists of indicators, namely procedures and socialization processes.Assess the organization's ability to socialize the program to stakeholders and build consensus, which includes socialization procedures and communication processes. 3) Adaptation:namely the ability of an organization to adapt to its environment. Adaptation consists of indicators, namely increasing capabilities and infrastructure.Measuring the organization's ability to adapt to environmental changes, including improving HR skills and optimizing infrastructure.

ASN Competency Development

ASN competency development is an effort to improve individual abilities and capacities according to organizational needs. Competence can be interpreted as an individual's ability to produce performance that meets the required standards. The core of competence lies in the capacity or behavior possessed by an employee or staff in carrying out their duties and functions effectively. In relation to this, it is important to establish competency standards that serve as a reference for civil servant resources. This standard aims for civil servants to have clear guidance in developing the necessary knowledge, skills, and behavior. Spencer and Spencer (2008)[9]identifies five types of competency characteristics, namely motives, traits, self-concept, knowledge, and skills. The relevant apparatus needs to refer to this standard to ensure that the competencies they possess are able to provide significant contributions to achieving the organization's goals, objectives, indicators, and targets. Thus, competency development becomes an important element in ensuring the effectiveness of organizational performance.

Blended learning

*Blended learning*is a learning method that combines face-to-face learning with online learning[10]. blended learning utilizes modern technology to create an interactive and flexible learning process. This method allows participants to learn independently through technology-based applications and evaluations, while also receiving direct guidance from facilitators in face-to-face sessions.Blended learning refers to learning that combines or mixes face-to-face learning and online learning. The most common terms for this term are hybrid course, which means combination or mixture, and blended, which means learning. Blended learning is a training model that combines conventional face-to-face classical learning with online learning, either independently or collaboratively, using information and communication technology infrastructure.[3]

According to[2] in his research the use of blended learning certainly has advantages and disadvantages, namely: 1. Advantages of blended learning: a) This method can be used

flexibly. b) The existence of an online or offline or face-to-face learning system, by using this method the two learning systems can be combined to create better learning. c) The use of this method can make the learning system more effective and efficient. d) The existence of combination learning can help participants in accessing learning materials easily. 2. Disadvantages of blended learning: a) The availability of online learning facilities including computers, internet networks, and the latest smartphones is not evenly distributed, b) Participants' knowledge of the use of learning technology is still minimal.

Some studies on *blended learning* has been done. Risky Setiawan et al., in his research on the Effectiveness of Blended Learning in Educational Innovation in the Industrial Era 4.0 in the Classical Test Theory Course, concluded that blended learning is an active learning-based learning that is very good for implementation in higher education. Optimization of blended learning is carried out with [1] readiness of system facilities and mature planning, [2] development of complete and interesting content, [3] routine monitoring and evaluation of the learning process.[11]

3. RESEARCH METHODS

To find data on the effectiveness of the implementation of the blended learning method in leadership training at the BPSDM of Gorontalo Province, the researcher used a qualitative research approach. This approach emphasizes an in-depth understanding of the behavior, views, and experiences of the study subjects, by prioritizing the interpretation of phenomena in a natural context.

The method used is qualitative descriptive research, which aims to describe events or phenomena in research objects and analyze them in depth to provide solutions to identified problems. In this case, the research focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of implementing the blended learning method, including aspects of goal achievement, integration, and adaptation in leadership training. To obtain data, Data Collection techniques use the method: 1) Interview: The researcher prepared a semi-structured interview guideline covering key topics such as achieving training objectives, integration procedures, and technology adaptation in implementing blended learning. Informants included facilitators, training participants, and the implementing committee. 2) Observation:

Observations were conducted by going directly to the training location at the BPSDM of Gorontalo Province. Researchers directly observed the training process, both face-to-face and online, and recorded interactions between participants, facilitators, and the technology used. 3) Documentation Study: Documentation study was conducted by reviewing related documents, such as training guidelines, activity schedules, blended learning training policies, and participant evaluation results. The data analysis technique used in this study follows the Miles and Huberman model, which consists of three stages: 1) Data Reduction: Summarizing and filtering data that is relevant to the research focus. Irrelevant data will be eliminated to maintain clarity and focus of the analysis. 2) Data Presentation: Data is presented in narrative, table, or diagram form to facilitate understanding and further analysis. 3) Drawing Conclusions: Initial conclusions are drawn based on patterns or themes that emerge from the data. These findings are verified to ensure their accuracy and validity before being formulated into final conclusions.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Goal Achievement

Blended learning-based leadership training at BPSDM Gorontalo Province showed a significant increase in effectiveness in achieving training objectives. Based on the dimensions of "target" and "time period" according to Duncan, this method succeeded in increasing the percentage of graduation from 96% in 2021 (before implementation) to 100% in 2022 and

98.9% in 2023. In addition, the quality of training outcomes also increased, with participants who received very satisfactory scores increasing from 40% in 2021 to 64.3% in 2023. This increase reflects the success of blended learning in improving the managerial competence of participants, which is one of the main targets of the training. This is in line with the opinion of Alliger and Janak (2001)[12] that the effectiveness of training can be measured by achieving results that are in accordance with objectives.

blended learning support time and resource efficiency, which is a demand for bureaucratic modernization. The duration of face-to-face training is reduced from 31–35 days in the classical method to 15–18 days with the blended learning method. This reduction is offset by flexible online sessions, allowing participants to arrange their learning schedules without disrupting their work responsibilities. As stated by Staker and Horn (2012)[13], blended learning provides flexible access to learning at any time, supporting the improvement of human resource quality more effectively.

However, challenges remain, especially in maintaining participant focus during online learning. Some participants reported difficulty concentrating because they still had to handle work responsibilities, even though there was a policy of exemption from work. This shows the importance of creating a supportive learning environment, as stated by Kahn (1990)[14], that participant engagement is key to successful learning. Another obstacle is the limited technology infrastructure in some locations, which can hinder the smooth running of online sessions.

In addition to supporting time efficiency, blended learning also encourages an increase in the quality of participant understanding. Participants not only graduate, but also demonstrate better mastery of training materials, as evidenced by the increase in grade qualifications. According to Moenir (2001)[15], effective training not only improves the basic skills of the apparatus, but also encourages career development and employee performance. In the context of bureaucratic reform, the success of such training is an important indicator of the success of the competency development program.

The flexibility of this method also facilitates various learning formats, such as self-paced and distance learning. Participants can set their own learning pace, utilize technology to enhance interaction with facilitators, and still carry out their work responsibilities. Research by Sulila et al. (2024)[16] shows that technology that supports e-government can improve the effectiveness of training and public services.

Overall, blended learning at BPSDM Gorontalo Province showed positive results in supporting the achievement of training targets. Increased graduation, learning quality, and efficiency of training duration indicate that this method is in line with the demands of modern public administration. However, obstacles such as difficulty in focusing participants and limited technological infrastructure need more attention to optimize implementation. With the right supporting policies, blended learning has great potential to continue to improve the effectiveness of leadership training and human resource development of civil servants, in accordance with the goals of bureaucratic reform and modernization of public administration.

2. Integration

Integration dimensions according to Duncan (in Steers, 2020)[5] includes procedures and socialization processes. In implementing blended learning training, BPSDM Gorontalo Province has prepared implementation procedures based on LAN guidelines, including planning, implementation stages, and code of conduct arrangements. This procedure is the foundation for successful training, although challenges such as sudden schedule changes often affect the readiness of facilitators and participants. Scheduling stability is essential to ensure that all parties can prepare themselves well and that training can run according to plan. This

is in accordance with the views of Gulick and Urwick (1937)[17]that thorough planning in public administration is the key to successful program implementation.

Socialization, as the second element in integration, plays an important role in ensuring that participants and facilitators understand the training procedures, including the use of the Learning Management System (LMS). Although initial socialization has been carried out, some participants felt unprepared because they had to learn the LMS while taking the training. The same thing was felt by the facilitator, who considered that information related to the LMS was not completely clear during the preparation meeting. This condition indicates the need for more in-depth and repeated socialization before the training begins. In public administration, effective communication is very important to create a shared understanding, as stated by Sukirno (2024)[18]. Good communication supports organizational adaptation and ensures smooth program implementation.

As an improvement effort, BPSDM has provided video tutorials, Zoom sessions, and involved a mentoring committee to assist participants and facilitators who need additional guidance. The role of the mentoring committee is vital in answering questions, providing explanations, and ensuring the smooth running of the training. Collaboration between participants, facilitators, and mentoring committee reflects the importance of teamwork in public administration, as expressed by Ekonomika et al. (2024)[19]that good cooperation increases the efficiency and effectiveness of training program implementation.

In conclusion, integration in the implementation of blended learning at BPSDM Gorontalo has not been fully achieved. Obstacles such as lack of understanding of LMS and unstable schedules still affect the effectiveness of the training. However, with clearly structured implementation procedures and the support of the role of the accompanying committee, the training has shown quite good results. To achieve optimal integration, improvements are needed in socialization with more structured communication and consistency in training scheduling. This effort will not only increase the effectiveness of training but also support the goals of bureaucratic reform through the development of better apparatus competencies.

3. Adaptation

Adaptation in the implementation of the blended learning method is very important to ensure that all parties—facilitators, participants, and the organizing committee—can adjust to changes in learning that combine face-to-face and online. Adaptation dimensions according to Duncan (in Steers, 2020)[5]highlights the organization's ability to face changes and challenges in its implementation. In the context of this training, facilitators are required to be able to use technology such as LMS (Learning Management System) to manage interactive learning and deliver materials effectively in two modes. Participants must also master technology and have high motivation to learn independently and collaboratively. Support for facilities such as technological infrastructure and appropriate learning materials are determining factors for the success of this adaptation.

However, the adaptation process does not always run smoothly. Based on interviews, some facilitators still have difficulty using the LMS and tend to use traditional teaching methods that are less suited to the characteristics of blended learning. Although some have succeeded in adapting, this success is not evenly distributed, so additional training is needed to improve the facilitator's abilities. On the participant side, challenges in mastering technology and adapting to new learning methods also affect the effectiveness of the training. The support of facilities and infrastructure provided by BPSDM, such as the flexible Langga LMS, classrooms, and other physical facilities, are positive steps in creating a conducive learning environment.

Adequate facilities show the organization's commitment to adapting to change. This is in line

with the theory of transformational leadership (Silalahi, 2011)[20]which emphasizes the importance of innovation and support to ensure the organization is responsive to change. Transformational leadership at BPSDM is evident from their efforts in providing facilities that support technological needs and ensuring that training continues despite challenges. In addition, continuous evaluation of the capabilities of all parties involved and improvement of training facilities are essential so that the adaptation process can continue to improve.

The success of this adaptation can be seen from the ability of the parties involved to adapt to the blended learning method and utilize the available facilities. With this effort, training has been able to create a flexible learning environment and support effectiveness. As stated by Mokhber et al. (2018), innovative leadership can encourage organizational commitment to stay focused on goals through the implementation of new approaches.[21].

In conclusion, adaptation in the implementation of the blended learning method at BPSDM Gorontalo has shown positive results, both in terms of technology mastery by facilitators and participants, as well as adequate support for facilities. Although not yet fully optimal, continuous improvement in training and infrastructure provision will further support the achievement of training objectives, namely improving the competence of human resources of civil servants.

5. CLOSING

Based on the research results and discussion, the researcher formulated several conclusions as follows:

1. The implementation of the blended learning method in leadership training at BPSDM Gorontalo Province showed an increase in achieving training objectives. This can be seen from the increase in the percentage of participants passing and the quality of the grades achieved, although there are still challenges related to time flexibility and disruption of participants' work. The flexibility of this method allows for efficiency of time and resources, but adjustments are still needed to ensure consistency of participant focus.
2. The integration dimension, which includes procedures and socialization processes, is not yet fully optimal. The implementation procedure has been running well based on LAN guidelines, but challenges such as sudden schedule changes and less in-depth LMS socialization affect the smoothness of the training. Efforts such as improving scheduling stability and increasing socialization before training are needed to achieve better integration.
3. Adaptation to the blended learning method has shown positive results, with increased capabilities of facilitators, participants, and the organizing committee in managing technology-based learning. Support for facilities such as LMS Langga and adequate physical facilities also support this success. However, the uneven mastery of technology among facilitators and participants is an obstacle that needs to be overcome through additional training and ongoing evaluation. Better adaptation will strengthen the effectiveness of training in supporting the improvement of state apparatus HR competencies.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. HW Maningar, Sujarwoto, and IGEPS Sentanu, "Effectiveness of Implementing Training Models *Blended learning* In State Apparatus Leadership Training (Study on the Implementation of Leadership Training at the State Administration Institution of the Republic of Indonesia)," *J. Adm. Publik*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 258–264, 2020.
2. L. Yunhang and D. Hidayati, "Implementation *Blended learning* at Maria Regina Elementary School School Implementation of Blended Learning at Maria Regina

- Elementary School Semarang,” *J. Educator. Manaj.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 50–60, 2023, doi: 10.12928/jimp.v3i1.6333.
3. A. Akhmadi, “Implementation of *Blended learning* in Training,” *J. Religious Education*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 78–87, 2021.
 4. H. Erman, “The Importance of Training for Civil Servants to Improve Civil Servant Competence,” *Sumbarprov.Go.Id*, 2020.
 5. RM Steers, *Organizational Effectiveness*, Management Series. Jakarta: Erlangga, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://onsearch.id/Author/Home?author=Steers%2C+Richard+M>.
 6. I. Rodiyah, H. Sukmana, and L. Mursyidah, *Introduction to Public Administration Science*. Umsida Press, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://press.umsida.ac.id/index.php/umsidapress/article/view/978-623-6292-31-0/1049>
 7. F. Asharri and RS Astuti, “The Effectiveness of Village Governance in the Implementation of Village Funds in Wringinjajar Village,” *J. Public Policy ...*, pp. 1–18, 2019, [Online]. Available: <https://ejournal3.undip.ac.id/index.php/jppmr/article/view/24124>
 8. RH Mokoginta, JH Posumah, and N. Palar, “Effectiveness of Using the Aspiration Clinic and Complaint Service (KINALANG) Application in the New Normal Era in Kotamobagu City,” *Community Participation in Prevention and Handling of Corona Virus in Teling Atas Village, Wanea District, Manado City*, vol. VII, no. 102, pp. 43–52, 2021.
 9. Y. Abdussamad, “Development of Human Resources of Civil Servants Through Competence,” *J. Econ. and Business*, pp. 1–6, 2017, [Online]. Available: <https://www.academia.edu/download/50498885/Pemembangan-Sumber-Daya-Manusia-Aparatur-Melalui-Kompetensi.pdf>
 10. Hussein, *Blended learning*. Jakarta: Prestasi Pustaka, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://scholar.google.co.id/citations?user=CUBCCX8AAAAJ&hl=en>
 11. R. Setiawan, D. Mardapi, A. Pratama, and S. Ramadan, “Effectiveness *blended learning* in educational innovation in the industrial era 4.0 in the classical test theory course,” *J. Inov. Technol. Educator.*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 148–158, 2019, doi: 10.21831/jitp.v6i2.27259.
 12. M. Madaniet al., “EFFECTIVENESS OF MENTAL REVOLUTION TRAINING IMPLEMENTATION AT TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT CENTER,” vol. 8, 2022.
 13. Pijar, “Hybrid Learning and *Blended learning* Complete Guide,” Pijar Sekolah. [Online]. Available: <https://pijarsekolah.id/blog/apa-itu-blended-learning-dan-bedanya-dengan-hybrid-learning/>
 14. AM Munthe, N. Jayanti, and M. Raja, “Job Engagement and Employee Well-being,” vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2023.
 15. Yuslim, “Development of Human Resources of Civil Servants in Improving Public Services at the Tanggarong Sub-district Office, Kutai Kartanegara Regency,” *J. Adm. Reform*, vol. 1, no. 42, pp. 569–581, 2014.
 16. I. Sulila, IR Santoso, M. Polin, R. Lukum, and W. Gobel, “Development of E-Government Public Policy Implementation Model in Online Tax Services,” vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 70–83, 2024, doi: 10.22495/jgrv13i3art6.
 17. DA Anwaruddin and M. Ed, “THE RISE AND Ebb of PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION PARADIGM By: The Existence of Public Administration,” vol. 6, pp. 1–16, 2014, [Online]. Available:

<https://jia.stialanbandung.ac.id/index.php/jia/article/download/192/140/703>

18. Z. Sukirno, "Redefinition of Administrative Communication- Public Administration Study Program," pp. 56–73, 2024.
19. J. Ekonomika, D. Bisnis, V. No, and S. Oktober, "The Effect of Teamwork and Communication on Employee Performance at the Capital Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office (Dpmptsp) of Palembang City," vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 1161–1171, 2024.
20. AF Fanani, MM Iqbal, W. Astutik, and Y. Lestari, "Transformational Leadership in the Public Sector," *JPSI (Journal Public Sect. Innov.*, vol. 4, no. 2, p. 84, 2020, doi: 10.26740/jpsi.v4n2.p84-90.
21. A. Hidayat and A. Subowo, "INNOVATIVE LEADERSHIP IN REALIZING PUBLIC SERVICE INNOVATION IN SEMARANG CITY HEALTH OFFICE," pp. 1–12, 2023.